

**THE INFLUENCE OF THE VALUE SYSTEM OF SOCIALLY ACTIVE
TEENAGERS ON THE VOCATIONAL QUALITIES**

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Annotation. Values are considered as a connecting link for the inclusion of a teenager in collective activities, in the process of understanding and realizing the values of a certain society, and provide methods of managing social behavior in accordance with the values and goals of the activities of social groups. In the process of accumulating life experience, personal values develop, which include a semantic, emotionally experienced, personal attitude to life. The value system of a teenager's personality is considered to be of great importance and has an impact on his formation as a person. In this article, we tried to shed light on the value system of the adolescent personality and its place in its activities.

Keywords: personality, adolescent, value, value system, thinking, behavior, self-awareness, education, feelings, activity.

Introductory part. Today's reform period calls for the creation of effective methods of teaching, further expansion of cooperation between teachers and adolescents, ensuring the leadership of education in the formation of human personality, taking into account the youth characteristics and national feelings of adolescents. acquisition requires the implementation of educational activities. Therefore, it is time to study the socio-psychological characteristics of adolescents, their potential, to confidently look at their future, and to form sufficient knowledge and skills about their place in life.

Discussion. It is natural that today's psychological processes, with their various forms, attract inquisitive young people, future professionals, and teenagers. Therefore, the human psyche is always growing, growing, developing, maturing, and seeing, perceiving, thinking, making complex observations, all kinds of events, events, experiences, family, work, science, country, country. It is not limited to the necessary truths that a horse can believe.

The problem of values is being actively discussed and studied within various scientific directions. Currently, there is increasing interest in the problem of formation of individual values based on the destruction of the existing social value system, re-evaluation of personal values. Let's turn to the concept of "value". S.I.Ojigova's dictionary defines the term value as follows: "Value is important. It means spiritual values, cultural values, and material values."

The fact that the value orientations of the person are currently being studied at the philosophical, sociological, pedagogical, individual psychological and socio-psychological levels confirms that it is one of the most important general scientific problems. Its importance lies in the fact that a person's value system occupies the place where his motives and world perception intersect, and performs the task of coordinating all types of behavior and human activity. Values and value orientations play an important role not only in the life of each individual, but also in the life of the whole society, which performs an integral function. Every person's choice in life is based on values. The values that occupy a central position in the formation of a teenager's personality have a significant impact on the orientation of a person and the content of his social activities, behavior and actions, his social status and general attitude towards the world, himself and other people.

Value orientations are the most important component of a teenager's mind, which significantly affects the perception of the environment, society, social group, and the individual's ideas about himself. As an element of a person's

structure, they reflect his internal readiness to act to satisfy needs and goals, give direction to his behavior in all spheres of activity. The peculiarity of value orientations is that this category is most closely related to the subject's behavior and controls this process as a conscious action.

Value orientations are a complex socio-psychological phenomenon that describes the direction and content of an active person, it is an integral part of the system of personal relationships, it determines the general attitude of a person to the world, to himself, to which he gives meaning and direction. will give. The system of value orientations has a multi-level structure. Its peak is values related to the ideals and life goals of a person.

Value orientations are formed in the process of assimilation of social experience and are found in goals, ideals, beliefs, interests and other aspects of personality. In the structure of human activity, value orientations are closely related to its cognitive and volitional aspects. The system of value orientations constitutes the substantive aspect of the individual's orientation and represents the internal basis of his attitude to reality.

The urgency of studying the value orientations of adolescents led to the emergence of a number of works devoted to various aspects of this problem.

Literature analysis. Since values exist as the essence, importance, and content of forms of reality, they determine the practical activities of people, and people must adjust their lifestyles to their requirements.

The problem of values is related to the research conducted by scientists and practitioners such as M.V.Boguslovsky, K.V.Gavrilovets, B.S.Gershunsky, V.V.Ilyin, V.A.Karakovsky, N.D.Nikandrov, L.I.Novikova, V.A.Slastenin and others.

The problem of forming the value direction of teenagers is revealed in the works of L.P.Bueva, I.S.Kon, N.D.Nikandrova, A.S.Sharov and others.

Philosophical and sociological foundations of the development of the value

system in students were researched by A.Begmatov, M.Bekmuradov, V.Kanke, J.Kim, M.Kaxharova, Q.Nazarov, N.Rozov, I.Surina, J.Tulenov, E.Yusupov . Psychologists such as Sh.Barotov, M.Davletshin, A.Jabborov, V.Karimova, L.Kunts, L.Mitina, N.Safayev, A.Seriy, E.Goziyev, A.Sharov, G.Shoumarov, etc. researched.

A.N.Leontev believes that the main means of accepting social values is understood as "activity", that a personal meaning system is formed in the process of communication and activity. D.A. Leontev connects the concept of value with three different groups of phenomena and states that there are three different values:

- 1) in the ideals of society;
- 2) in the actions or works of certain people;
- 3) in motivational structures of the individual.

The object of value attraction, in general, appears as the meaning of existence. The important thing is that the value does not come from the object itself, but from the attitude towards it from the point of view of the subject. Values can be divided into two groups: material (utilitarian) and spiritual (high) values. Alternatively, the division of values into groups is relative. S.A.Lebedev defines values as universal goals and standards (norms). S.Yu.Golovin considers values as the product of life activity, which is the subject of groups and social units, the entire human life.

The system of values is so multifaceted and diverse that it is among the topics that require careful consideration and description. The increasing complexity of human life and the increasing demand for a good life lead to the recognition that the value system is nothing more than a personal decision.

M.Rokich studied the problem of values and trends. It is appropriate to dwell on the classification of values according to M.Rokich, because the scientist divided all human values into two large categories:

- terminal - a person's belief that the final goal is worth all efforts to achieve it;
- instrumental - a person's belief that a certain method of behavior and actions is the most successful for achieving a goal.

S.Schwartz and U.Bilisky have also done great work in the field of values and offer some signs of values, namely:

- the concept of values means belief and trust;
- they have the nature of controlling the state of a person or his behavior;
- they have a supersituational character;
- leads in the selection, as well as in the assessment of people's behavior and actions;
- they are sorted by importance.

It should be said that value represents the ideas about oneself, which are distinguished by the management of a person's activities. If these two attitudes are closely related to each other, we can call them personal values.

Results and analyses. Today, among the instrumental values that teenagers put first, the following can be included: responsibility, sense of duty; decency and courage in defending one's thoughts and views; cheerfulness and honesty; tolerance (the views and opinions of others, the ability to forgive others);

The value orientations of adolescents who have fallen into a bad social situation differ in many ways from the value orientations of adolescents raised in good conditions. It is among the values of teenagers who have fallen into a bad social situation. does not include qualities such as tolerance, sensitivity, responsibility. Teenagers are sure that nothing depends on them, they are not interested in social recognition, but only in their personal status in society.

The impact of unfavorable and inhuman conditions in the family on the life of a teenager causes negative physical and mental changes in the child's body for

a long time, which leads to serious consequences. It causes deviations in the behavior and personal development of the teenager. They are distinguished by the following: lack of value orientations, moral and ethical norms, inability to adapt to new conditions, as well as bad habits (alcohol, drugs, smoking), etc.

Thus, our research showed that the most obvious characteristics of values-oriented teenagers are:

- approximately half of adolescents have a low level of moral position, collectivism;
- 45% of strong-willed qualities have a high level of development;
- self-knowledge, mental self-control, self-development, psychological culture are weakly expressed in about half of adolescents;
- among the main values of teenagers there are "financial support", "successful education", "well-being of family and loved ones" and "health";
- the most difficult values for teenagers are "glory", "rest and entertainment" and "opportunity to engage in creativity";
- most teenagers are satisfied with their current life;
- most teenagers believe that their personal characteristics, personal characteristics, are the reason for their success and failure;
- more than half of teenagers (55%) have a high level of civic self-awareness, civic duties and respect for laws.

Therefore, value orientations are a specially structured and hierarchical system of expressing values that express the subjective attitude of a person to the objective conditions of life, determine the actions and actions of a person in reality, are manifested and revealed in practical behavior.

In conclusion. In conclusion, we must say that it is necessary to ensure the leadership of education in the formation of a Christian personality, to take into account the youth characteristics and national feelings of adolescents, and to implement educational activities. For this reason, it would be appropriate to study

the social and psychological characteristics of adolescents, their possibilities, to look at their future with confidence, to find their place in life, and to form sufficient knowledge and skills in them about values. was Because value orientations are the main characteristic of a person, the basis of a person's social emergence.

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